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A non-static God concept

Abstract

What would it be like if God were open to what happens in the next moment? If he would walk with his creation every day? If he would continuously create the moment out of change? About the consequences of a non-static concept of God.

Main Part

Panentheism and process theology are two schools of thought within contemporary theology that views creation not as a static event, but as endowed with dynamism. The idea of God as a becoming is the concept of process theology and panentheism, Jewish as well as Christian with small differences. If one takes seriously the idea that the whole world, the whole universe is His body and this body, this universe is changing, then also the creator must necessarily change in time.

Theists believe that God is neither identical with the world, nor is he separated from it. In the sense of a panentheism (from gr. "all in God"), however, the transcendence of God is connected with his immanence in the world. There is no "outside of God" - the whole world is his body. So He is even more than omnipresent as he is all that exists. So both - world and God reality and the universe are defined by processes of change.

Therefore, process theologians do not longer speaks of God's being, but of His becoming. God is no longer static. The entire world consists of interrelationships in which God is involved. So with every action, may it even be as innocent as the flight of a butterfly, God changes.

He is directly influenced by the events in the world, in real time. He reacts to what happens in the and is himself changed by the becoming of the world. The world is, so to speak, the creative undertaking of God - and conversely, He himself is the event of creative transformation of the world.

This is necessarily accompanied by another paraphrase: God's omnipotence is redefined and partially negated; God never uses coercion to carry out his will, but enables a world of self-creation in which subjects have room for free choice. God and His creation as a unity with a core that goes far beyond creation - interpenetrated and interconnected. This model is not reserved for process theology and panentheism alone; other theologians of creation from the Neoplatonists to Master Eckhart also prefer it.

Process theology finds in all events always at the same time God and nature, creation and evolution, God's action and the laws of physics, biology, astronomy at work. So there is no sequence of natural events in history, such as the emergence of new species, which is new species, which are interrupted by leaps, in which only God works. God is the origin of the new and of order. God does not create the world out of nothing (*creatio ex nihilo*), but is a dynamic, constantly continuing process of the emergence of something new (*creatio continua*). God is therefore not the determining Initiator, who has determined everything from the outset, but is completely involved in the world and its development, as God the one and threefold.

Conclusion

God is in all things, but everything is also in God. He is all that exists, without any exception. However, God is at the same time also transcendent. The world is immanent in and through him. Trinity has a broader and deeper meaning than most people believe.

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